

USING CLAUDE 3.7 SONNET + PROJECT TO BUILD A UNIVERSITY ARCHIVES METADATA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract - Can an archivist with limited programming experience build a working metadata management application using only AI tools as technical support? As we enter an age when AI tools are ubiquitous, we will increasingly rely on these tools to expedite, optimize, and contribute to our archival and digital preservation job requirements.

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Keywords - AI, code development, metadata, archives, integration.

Conference Topics - Haerenga - Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

This project is inspired by the work of Hudhayfa Nazoordeen, a 20-year student at the University of Waterloo who built a proof-of-concept nuclear fusor in his bedroom. In Nazoordeen's post describing the project, he stated that he had "zero hardware experience" and his secret of success, "Claude Sonnet 3.5 + Project" [1]. Our project challenge, an order of magnitude less ambitious, is to build a proof-of-concept, functional, and integrated University Archives Metadata Management System (UAMMS). As AI tools increase in capability, it is valuable to investigate how far a traditional archivist with limited development experience can get in building a comprehensive metadata management service. Additionally, it has been a valuable learning experience in the strengths and weaknesses of the current generation of AI tools.

AI-Assisted Development Strategy

This section of the poster will describe and explain the planning and strategy of using Claude 3.7 + Project to develop the UAMMS. It will provide a brief description of Claude 3.7 and clearly explain the Project feature of the Anthropic LLM. Additionally, it will provide a brief description of the requirements for the proof-of-concept project.

II. TECHNICAL IMPLEMENTATION WITH CLAUDE

This section will focus on the technical process of using Claude to develop the UAMMS. It will include sections describing the application's architecture, prerequisite metadata normalization requirements, code generation process, data ingestion and validation, and error resolution techniques. The visual component of the poster will incorporate images of the prompts used in the project and images showcasing the gradual evolution of the UAMMS application.

III. CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS IN AI-ASSISTED DEVELOPMENT

This section will describe the process prompt conditioning Claude to yield more relevant prompt responses and code generation. It will summarize the project's significant challenges, including AI-assisted development's current limitations and drawbacks. To provide contextual positioning, it will

reference similar projects in AI-assisted development.

IV. RESULTS, BENEFITS, AND NEXT STEPS

The proof-of-concept development of the UAMMS was successful, yet it had several drawbacks. Principally, the code base for the application may require significant revisions before it is stable and fully integrated as our primary metadata management interface. This section will briefly describe the results and benefits of AI code-assisted development. It will also outline the project's next steps, including further development, external evaluation and feedback, and continued implementation and integration.

V. CONCLUSION

Claude 3.7 Sonnet + Project proved to be an effective method for supporting the development of a metadata management tool with minimal programming experience required. This project demonstrates that the current state of AI-assisted code development is more beneficial for those with limited programming experience. Experienced programmers may find the code generated by current LLMs overly elaborate and in need of many revisions. Claude tended to be unnecessarily verbose when developing product documentation and code. A persistent stream of limiting prompts was required to whittle down Claude's outputs to fit the project scope and requirements. Even as LLM and other AI tools continue to advance, a human actor must be involved in specifying requirements and evaluating whether the AI outputs meet those requirements.

and consortia domains. His professional interests include digital preservation, archival collection assessment, and research data management.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. Nazoordeen [@hud_zah], in a couple weeks, i built a nuclear fusor in my bedroom – with zero hardware experience, X, Aug 23, 2024. Available: https://x.com/hud_zah/status/1827057785995141558 (accessed: Mar. 23, 2025).

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Eamon Smallwood is the University Archivist at King Abdullah University of Science and Technology. He earned his Master of Library of Information Science from the University of Denver in 2009. He has experience working in academic, government,

